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**The Importance of Tawhīdic Epistemology in the
Modern Science Education Curriculum**

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ABSTRACT

It is essential to point out that the character of Islamic religious doctrine is constructed on the basis of monotheistic belief known as tawhīd. However, one of the major problems that have been encountered by the Muslim ummah in the modern education curriculum is the secularization of knowledge's. Since it is secular in nature, the inclusion of God across the modern curriculum is being ignored. It is known that the essence of holistic Islamic education is to develop not only the human cognitive and physical aspects but also the spiritual sides. Therefore, tawhīdic epistemology must be reintroduced across the modern secular education curriculum such as science. This paper will analyze the importance and roles of tawhīdic epistemology in the modern science education curriculum by referring to the main source of this epistemology, the Qur'ān. Thus, it is hope that the arguments given in this paper can possibly become a teaching source for both religious and science educators. Apart from that, the author will elaborate the effects towards the future ummah due to the loss of tawhīdic epistemology. Therefore, showing the necessity of this epistemology for the Muslim education curriculum in today's modern era.

INTRODUCTION

Most of the modern science education curriculum nowadays has been influence by the western secular philosophy, which generally ignored the inclusion of God. One of the reasons is due to the introduction of modern secular education during the colonial era (Osman Bakar, 2008). As the secular education is mostly associated with empirical knowledge, the possible end product of this education will produce human that are atheist in nature. For a Muslim, the modern secular education cannot be an ideal model for the development of the future *ummah*. Thus, these types of education should be modified and develop with a tawhīdic epistemology that are more holistic in nature.

The word "epistemology" is rooted from the Greek word "episteme" and "logos", which both denotes "knowledge" and " the study or the science of" (Truncellito, 2007). It inquires into the nature of knowledge and justification of belief. According to Azram (2011), many writers prefer to use the label "The theory of knowledge". Thus, tawhīdic epistemology is the theory of knowledge based on the principles of tawhīd, the defining doctrine of Islam which declares "absolute monotheism-the unity and uniqueness of God as creator and sustainer of the universe" (Esposito, 2014).

According to Osman Bakar in his article entitled "Identity Crisis: The Loss of Tawhīdic Epistemology As Its Root Cause" argues that the Muslim modern education in the colonial era based on secular epistemologies quickened the decline of tawhīdic epistemology. Thus, to the point of making it helpless to respond effectively to the challenges posed by those modern epistemologies. Therefore, these unresolved intellectual conflict between the surviving elements of tawhīdic epistemology and

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modern epistemologies has resulted in an epistemological crisis towards the life and thought of a Muslim.

Ibrahim Kalin as stated in Isham Pawan Ahmad (2014) argued that the most common attitude in the Islamic world is the lack of ethical as well as puritanical view of science. This will lead to environmental crisis, positivism, materialism and others, which are all related to modern science in one way or another. Thus by adding the tawhīdic dimension to the practise and teaching of science, these problems could be resolved. The major reason why Muslims in the past are able to find solution of problems faced by the Muslim community is due to the conformity with the Islamic worldview in God, man, nature and society that are closely intertwined and harmoniously interrelated which are manifested by the spiritual, moral as well as ethical values of Islam (Osman Bakar, 2008).

TAWHĪDIC APPROACH TOWARDS SCIENCE EDUCATION.

During the golden age of Islam, scientific culture or education was widely initiated and established by the Muslims. Osman Bakar (2014) stated that the core content of Islamic civilization is the principle of unity (tawhīd) and its manifestations at every levels of cosmic and microcosmic existence that can be understood as both individual and collective human existence.

The term 'tawhīd' strictly means monotheism. However, it is usually used in a broader sense that it acquired through its doctrinal usage to include the Qur'ānic discussions of God's existence. Therefore, it can be understood as "the existence and uniqueness of God" as manifested in His creation. A well-known American Muslim scholar, Robert Dikson Crane (2012) defined tawhīd as the coherent diversity in all of creation that points to the Oneness of its origin. It is indeed the key to Islamic epistemology. According to Alpraslan Acikgenc (2014), the Qur'ān over-emphasizes the oneness of God's not only because it was sent to a society where polytheism (*Shirk*) was widespread, but also due to human tendency to easily fall into the trap of polytheism' and sometimes, unconsciously by raising certain selfish objectives to a divine status. Thus, it is very vital to understand the main concept of tawhīd as one of the component of faith in Islam, so that science that will be acquired does not contradict with the Islamic faith.

The notion of God is the core of every religion, thus, in Islam; it is a central idea of the Qur'ān, which develops the idea of God. Acikgenc (2014) stated that almost one third of the Qur'ān is devoted to establishing this notion of God in the hearts and minds of humanity. This is the reason why it is important for us to capture the essence of this notion as it is represented in the world structure of Islamic worldview. If we comprehend what the Qur'ān means by the idea of God, we shall not only comprehend one third of the Qur'ānic messages but also its significance in human life, scientific as well as philosophical thought as every verses of it has a significant and implication towards human life as well as behaviour toward God and His creation.

The idea of unity of nature for instance, according to Nasr (2007), is derived from the application of the first principle of *al-tawhīd* contained in the first *shahādah*, *Lā ilāhā 'llāh* to the domain of nature, which noted the interrelatedness of all things that exist in the whole universe. Since the study of Science is regarded as the study of universe, it is related to the study of *tawhīd* or *Usūluddīn*. It is God, the Creator, who controlled the whole universe and it is *tawhīd* that generally understood as the study of God.

In the understanding of Islām, everything in the universe is an *āyah*. It is a sign which the Qur'ān repeats this truth frequently. The verses regarding are as follows:

سُزِيهِمْ ءَايَاتِنَا فِي الْأَفَاقِ وَفِي أَنْفُسِهِمْ حَتَّىٰ يَتَبَيَّنَ لَهُمْ أَنَّهُ
الْحَقُّ أَوَّلَ مَا يَكْفُرُ بِرَبِّكَ أَنَّهُ عَلَىٰ كُلِّ شَيْءٍ شَهِيدٌ ﴿٥٣﴾

“We will show them Our signs in the horizons and within themselves until it becomes clear to them that it is the truth. But is it not sufficient concerning your Lord that He is, over all things, a Witness?” [Sūrah Fussilat, 41:53]

Tawhīd is also associated with the knowledge related to the nature of God. According to Al-Attas (1995), the conception of the nature of God that is derived from the Revelation (i.e. Qur’ān) is also established upon the foundations of reason and intuition, and in some cases it is based on empirical intuition, as a result of man’s experience and consciousness of Him and of His creation. For instance, the Qur’ān says:

لَوْ كَانَ فِيهِمَا آلِهَةٌ إِلَّا اللَّهُ لَفَسَدَتَا فَسُبْحَانَ اللَّهِ رَبِّ الْعَرْشِ عَمَّا
يَصِفُونَ

“If there were, in the heavens and the earth, other gods besides Allah, there would have been confusion in both! but glory to Allah, the Lord of the Throne: (High is He) above what they attribute to Him!” [Surah al-'anbiyā, 21:22].

The above verse shows how the Qur’ān use rationality regarding the oneness of God. Men have to have knowledge in order to observe the empirical means. For instance, with the help of Astronomy, men will be able to observe the constant moving of planets, which reflects the One who controlled the system. The above verse also shows that the unity of the cosmos is a direct proof of Divine unity. This argument from God Himself could have only strengthened the Muslim scientist’s belief in the unity of the cosmos. Nevertheless, scientists also wanted to test the truth of their belief at scientific level. Thus, in their practise of science, they will found out that, the more they came to know nature of things, the more glaring the truth of unity of nature appeared to them, which proves the truth of Divine Unity. Therefore, science from Islamic perspective helps to instil a firm belief in the Unity of God. Thus it can be said that, science that is in accordance with the Qur’ān affirms *al-tawhīd*.

Figure 1: The relation between the Qur'ān, science and the affirmation of God (*al-Tawhīd*)

It must be understood that, the nature of God in Islamic perspective is not the same as the conceptions of God understood in the various religious traditions of the world. It is not the same as the conception of God understood in Greek or the Hellenistic philosophical tradition, nor as the conceptions of God understood in the Western philosophical or scientific tradition; nor in that of occidental and oriental mystical traditions. (Al-Attas, 1995)

It must be known that the essential message of the revelation (i.e. the Qur'ān) was always the same. It is to recognize, acknowledge as well as to worship Him (i.e. God) alone, without associating Him with any partner, rival nor attributing a likeness to Him. It is through revelation, in which God has descried Himself, His creative activity and His creation (*Ibid*). In regard with this, Al-Ghazālī has stated in his work entitled “al-Maqaṣad al-husnā fī ṣharḥ asmā' Allāh al-ḥusnā” (The ninety-nine beautiful names of God) has stated that there are two ways of knowing Him. One of them he said is the authentic way, which is by knowing his creation. Every creation that is moved to attain and perceive Him will be cast back by the splendour of His majesty. The second way is to know and learn the attributes and names of God. In the Qur'ān, it is often found that there are God attributes and names towards the end of the verse. This will enable the reader to reflect back to the Ultimate power that God has. The next discussion will focus on two main issues related the study of Astronomy, which are; the birth of the universe and the earth preservation, with reference to the verses of the Qur'ān that could reflect the role of tawhīdic epistemology in the modern education.

THE ROLE OF TAWHĪD ON THE BIRTH OF UNIVERSE

For ages, man has been asking the question of how the universe came into existence. He is interested in its age, its origin and its possible ending. Indeed, for hundreds of years, these questions have been posed and debated in various civilizations by philosophers, theologians, and scientists. Atheistic philosophers and scientists maintain the view that the universe does not demand a creator for its existence, since matter is eternal. They believed that “Matter can neither be created nor destroyed” (Ahmad Y. A.-H., 2010). In their view, the universe does not have an origin for it has always existed, as there was no time when it did not exist.

The idea of the birth of the universe raised the issue of the origin of time. In other words, if one believes that the universe has a beginning, does it mean that time is created as well? According to al-Ghazālī, time did not exist until the universe came into existence. Time and space are also created as components of the universe. Moreover, time is associated with motion and it is impossible for us to conceive of the existence of time before the creation of the universe.

From the point of view of modern science, the theory of relativity has shown that time has a relation to matter and space. Time, space and matter exist in a continuum. Their components must come together with respect to time in determining the existence of any entity in the physical universe (Hawking.S, 1988). It is interesting to note that al-Ghazālī's views about time and space are quite close to the views contained in the modern theory of relativity.

Since the Qur'ān maintains that God has created the universe, it does not accept the idea of eternity of matter. Actually, the first challenge to the theory of eternity of matter came when man discovered the phenomenon of radiation. Ahmad (2010) stated that the universe had existed for so long with the sun and all other blazing stars emitting radiation. If the stars and the sun existed from eternity then their fuel that produced radiation would have exhausted billions of years ago. Nevertheless, atheistic scientists deliberately ignore this fact. The atheistic scientists defended the idea that the universe is external and requires no creator. Georges Politzer, a French philosopher, in his book entitled *Principes Fondamentaux de Philosophie*, had opposed the idea of creation. He wrote: “The universe was not a created object; if it were, then it would have to be created instantaneously by God and brought into existence from nothing. To admit creation, one has to admit, in the first place, the existence of a moment when the universe did not exist, and that something came out of nothingness. This is something to which science cannot accede.” (Politzer, 1954, p. 84).

According to Qur'ān, it says:

أَوَلَمْ يَرِ الَّذِينَ كَفَرُوا أَنَّ السَّمَوَاتِ وَالْأَرْضَ كَانَا رَتْقًا
فَفَنَقْنَاهُمَا وَجَعَلْنَا مِنَ الْمَاءِ كُلَّ شَيْءٍ حَيٍّ أَفَلَا يُؤْمِنُونَ ﴿٣٠﴾

“Do the unbelievers not know that the heavens and the earth were joined together as one unit of creation, and then We clove them asunder? And We made from water every living thing. Will they not then believe?” [Surah Al-Anbiya, 21:30].

According to Ibn Kathir (Vol: 6, pg 440), this verse tells us about God’s perfect might and power in all of His creation and subjugation. This verse is specifically addressed to the regarding the birth of the universe as a proof of Allah’s existence, knowledge and power. Moreover, the last part of this verse which says “And We made from water every living thing. Will they not then believe?” further reminds the disbelievers of yet another proof of the existence of the Creator who is in control of all things. Therefore the inclusion of the above verses in the modern curriculum is critical in injecting the tawhīdic epistemology.

THE TAWHĪDIC SIGN ON THE EARTH PRESERVATION.

Our planet earth is the only planet in our solar system that is known to shelter life. The unique thin layers of atmosphere cause us to survive in which the layer separates us from the cold, airless void of space (Davies P., 2011). The Qur’ān reminds us to think about the creation of Earth so that we would acknowledge God as The Creator. The Qur’ān says:

لَخَلْقُ السَّمَوَاتِ وَالْأَرْضِ أَكْبَرُ مِنْ خَلْقِ النَّاسِ وَلَكِنَّ
أَكْثَرَ النَّاسِ لَا يَعْلَمُونَ ﴿٥٧﴾

“Assuredly the creation of the heavens and the earth is a greater (matter) than the creation of men: yet most men understand not (that all this is easy for Him).” [Surah Al-Ghafir, 40:57]

God has created the earth as a place for human beings to live in. The Qur’ān says:

الَّذِي جَعَلَ لَكُمُ الْأَرْضَ فِرَاشًا وَالسَّمَاءَ بِنَاءً وَأَنْزَلَ مِنَ السَّمَاءِ
مَاءً فَأَخْرَجَ بِهِ مِنَ الثَّمَرَاتِ رِزْقًا لَكُمْ فَلَا تَجْعَلُوا لِلَّهِ أَنْدَادًا
وَأَنْتُمْ تَعْلَمُونَ ﴿٢٢﴾

“[He] Who has made the earth a resting place for you, and the sky as a canopy; and sent down rain from the heavens; and brought forth therewith fruits for your sustenance; then do not set up rivals

unto Allah (in worship) while you know (that He alone has the right to be worshipped).” [Surah Al-Baqarah, 2:22]

For many scholars of *tafsīr* such as Ibn Kathir (2003, vol. 1), al-Razi and others, this verse provides a powerful argument for the existence of the Creator. Whoever reflects on created things will surely come to appreciate and comprehend the ability, wisdom, knowledge, perfection and majesty of their Creator.

According to Sayed Qutb in his *Tafsīr Fi Zilal Al-Qur’ān*, the verse 22 of *Surah Al-Baqarah* is a call for mankind as a whole to worship their Lord, who has created them. The final goal that worshippers want to accomplish is to become pious and righteous people who fear God and desist from every kind of sins and evil deeds that God forbids.

Commenting on the phrase “Who has made the earth a resting place for you”, Professor Zaghoul El-Naggar asserts that this verse refers to the purpose of the earth as a source of comfortable life and pleasant dwelling place for man. However people tend to forget that God is the one who created this earth for us to live in (El-Naggar, 2011). As for the phrase “sky as a canopy,” God has offered us with sophisticated construction of the sky in its immense dimensions with the numerous celestial bodies as well as the diverse types forces that protects this earth. The forces are:

1. Strong Nuclear force: one of the four basic forces in nature apart from gravity, the electromagnetic force and the weak nuclear force. However, it also has the shortest range implying that the particles must be extremely close before its effects could be observed. Its main function is to hold together the subatomic particles of the nucleus. Without this nuclear force, atomic nuclei would never be produced. A weak nuclear force is accountable for what are called radioactive elements. The weak force also enables the sun to provide us energy. Without this force, the universe would be worthless.
2. Electromagnetic force: It is a force that affects everything in the universe because like gravity it functions with an infinite range. It is also the force that unites atoms of matter together inside every molecule or compound. Without these forces, the universe would be loaded with atoms of loose compounds making it impossible for light and heat molecules to exist and thus for life itself.
3. Gravitational force: It is the force that holds and restrains together all sections of the sky, the stars, and heavenly objects. Without this force that bonds skies, stars and even galaxies, the earth and the sky would fall apart, the universe and all its components would scatter and even collide with one another.

The above forces are the most fundamental forces by which the earth is protected. It is on the God’s mercy to create these forces that make life on earth possible. As it is known, one of the six fundamental beliefs of a Muslim is to belief in the Day of Judgment or Hereafter. Both the Qur’ān and the Hadīth had emphasized the destruction of universe during the day of Hereafter. If God removes one of the fundamental forces that were mentioned above such as gravitational force, what will happen? Assuredly everything will be destroyed as collision between planets occurred. This proves the essentiality of modern knowledge in the understanding of faith and in return enhancing the role of tawhīdic epistemology across the modern education curriculum such as science.

THE SPHERICITY OF THE EARTH

Regarding the earth, the Qurān says:

وَالْأَرْضَ مَدَدْنَاهَا وَأَلْقَيْنَا فِيهَا رَوَاسِيَ وَأَنْبَتْنَا فِيهَا مِنْ كُلِّ شَيْءٍ مَّوْزُونٍ

“And the earth we have spread out; set therein mountains firm and immovable; and produced therein all kinds of things in due balance.” [Surah Al-Hijir, 15:19]

If we understand the phrase “the Earth is spread out” literally, then the earth may be taken as flat in shape. Factually, the earth is not flat. With the help of the latest technology developed, the Earth can clearly be seen from spaceships or satellites as a sphere rotating about its axis. Therefore, it is important to comprehend the real meaning of the Quranic phrase “and the earth we have spread out...” As explained by Ibn Kathir, by the words “spread out” Allah *Subhanahu wataala* means to convey the idea that He has made the earth such a vast place for human beings to live.

Syeikh Muhammad Mutawelli Sha’rawi commented that it is an example of the linguistic miracle of the Quran that it describes the apparent reality of the earth and also alludes to the true reality to be revealed by science. According to him, if we go to any locality on the earth, we will find it spread out. Whether we are at the South Pole or otherwise, in America or Europe or Africa or Asia or any other location on the Earth, we will observe the earth as spread out flat. This is only possible when the Earth is spherical. But if the Earth were to be rectangular or triangular or hexagonal or even any other shape, then if we will go to its edge, we will not see it spread out but instead see its edges. Therefore, the only shape that makes the Earth spread out at every position or locality is spherical shape. In addition, in such a case, if we begin to travel from any point on the surface of the Earth and return back to the initial point, we will discover the Earth spread out flat throughout the movement.

Sha’rawi further emphasizes that if the verse is correctly understood there would be no conflict between the Quran and science.

Moreover, the Quran provides other arguments to imply the spherical shape of the earth:

خَلَقَ السَّمَوَاتِ وَالْأَرْضَ بِالْحَقِّ يُكَوِّرُ اللَّيْلَ عَلَى النَّهَارِ وَيُكَوِّرُ
النَّهَارَ عَلَى اللَّيْلِ وَسَخَّرَ الشَّمْسَ وَالْقَمَرَ كُلٌّ يَجْرِي لِأَجَلٍ
مُسَمًّى أَلَا هُوَ الْعَزِيزُ الْغَفَّورُ

“He created the heavens and the earth in true (proportions): He makes the night overlap (*yukawwiru*) the day, and the day overlap the night: He has subjected the sun and the moon (to His Law): Each one follows a course for a time appointed. Is not He the Exalted In power - He who forgives again and again?” [Surah Az-Zumar, 39:5]

The above verse clearly shows that night and day occur in a cyclic form. Man’s cyclic experience of night and day relative to his position on Earth cyclically is only possible because of the Earth’s spherical shape, whereby half of the sphere (i.e. Earth) will be dark (i.e. night) and the other half will be bright (i.e. day). Such alternating positions of the earth are made possible by its rotation around its axis in facing towards the sun.

Ibn Kathir, Syed Qutub and other scholars of *tafsir* commented that the above verse clearly shows that Allah is the Creator of everything in the universe. He is the Sovereign and Controller of night and a day. According to Ibn Kathir, the Quranic verse which states: “He (i.e. Allah) makes the night to go in the day and makes the day to go in the night” tells us that Allah has subjugated them and causes them to

alternate without ceasing with each of them seeking the other rapidly. This fact is further clarified by the verse 54 of *Surah Al-A'raaf* that says:

“He (i.e. Allah) brings the night as a cover over the day, seeking it rapidly”. This verse is closely related to the verse 19 of *Surah Al-Hijir* that says:

“And He (i.e. Allah) has subjected the sun and the moon, each running for an appointed term.” Interpreters understand “for an appointed term” either to mean the time taken by each body to complete its orbit or to mean that the sun and the moon will eventually cease to exist. In my opinion, this verse also points to the Day of Resurrection, thus showing that in the Qur’an its scientific miracle goes hand in hand with issues of faith.

According to Danial Zainal Abidin (2007) the spherical shape of the earth is implied by the Arabic word “*kawwara*” in the verse 5, *Surah al-Zumar* already mentioned. In his *Al-Asas fi'l-tafsir*, Sa'id Hawa commented that the word “*yukawwiru*” comes from the word “*kawwara*,” meaning an act that involves a round-shaped object like a ball. He cites the example given by Imam Nasafi, namely the act of wearing the turban around the head. In his “A Dictionary Of Modern Arabic” Hans Wehr (1974) defines “*kawwara*” as “to roll, roll up, roll into a ball, to wind (the turban), to make round, ball-shaped.” By analogy, the covering of the earth by the day and the night in a similar way to the turban covering the head implies that the earth is of round shape.

The fact that the earth is spherical in shape was known to many leading scholars in the early history of Islam. In his book “*Majmu' al-Fataawa*” (Volume 6) Ibn Taimiyah stated that all celestial bodies including earth have a spherical shape as also believed by such *ulama* as Abu'l-Hasan Bin Al-Manaadi, Abu Muhammad Bin Hazm, Abdul-Faraj Bin Al-Jawzi and many more. Their view was based on the word “*falak*,” which means “sphere” or “round object.” According to Imam Abu Ya'la in his book “*Tabaqatal Hanabilah*” there is wide consensus (*ijma'*) among the Muslim scholars that the earth is spherical.

Another word in the Quran pointing to the sphericity of the earth is “*daha*.” The Quran says:

وَالْأَرْضَ بَعْدَ ذَلِكَ دَحَاهَا ﴿٣٠﴾

“And the earth, moreover, hath He (i.e Allah) extended (*daha*) (to a wide expanse);” [Surah An-Naziat, 79:30]

Said Hawa (1985) argues that the word “*daha*” demonstrates the linguistic miracle of the Quran. The word signifies something that is round like a ball. Thus the Arabs call the ostrich egg that is deepened inside the sand “*udhiyyah*” or “*udhuwwah*” which is derived from the word “*daha*” (Abidin, 2007). Therefore, the verse implies that the earth was made in a spherical shape like the ostrich egg.

Figure 1: Picture taken by Apollo 17 Crews on 25th March 2007.

(Picture obtained from: Coulter, 2009)

CONCLUSION

Islam distinguishes the quest for the two kinds of knowledge, making the one for the attainment of knowledge of the prerequisites of the first obligatory to all Muslims only, which is termed as “*fard ‘ayn*”, and the other obligatory to some Muslims only which is termed as “*fard kifāyah*” (al-Attas, 1995) Since *tawhīd* is closely related to the faith of a Muslim, it is considered as “*fard ‘ayn*”. Since, modern or natural science is only obligatory to some Muslims (i.e. “*fard kifāyah*”), it can be essential to develop the understanding of *tawhīd*. Therefore, before assessing through various type of knowledge such as science, we must begin with the Unity of God, which logically lead to the Unity of His creation. Thus, to develop the landmarks of Islamic education, the epistemology of *tawhīd* should be applied in the teaching of modern education such as science. To make that possible, the application of *tawhīd* epistemology across the modern curriculum should be applicable in the teacher training education program. If the epistemology of *tawhīd* is only exclusive to the religious education curriculum, which results in the loss of *tawhīd* epistemology among the Muslims who are in the “non-religious” stream such as science, there will be various kind of harmful thought and ideologies such as the atheists and secularists, who may harm the Muslim society in the future. Therefore, it is a necessity to reintroduce the epistemology of *tawhīd* rooted from the Divine sources (the Qur’ān and Hadīth) across the modern education curriculum.

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